

TEACHER'S SENSE OF SELF-EFFICACY TO PROBLEM BEHAVIOR AND THE ROLE OF ORGANIZATION CLIMATE IN REFERRAL AND REMOVAL

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Abstract: *Problem Behavior among young children in early childhood education centers are found to be at a growing rate from the literature. Problem behaviors if left untreated may lead to more severe outcomes for some children. Problem behaviors pose by young children in the early childhood classroom interrupt with classroom instruction. Early Identification which directs to early intervention is an evident based method to treat children at-risk of behavioral issues. Early intervention prepares children at-risk by providing an effective positive behavior support that may reduce the option of special education referral and removal from the mainstream environment. However problem behaviors in the early childhood classroom is remain under recognized or not widely addressed. Literature reports that, teachers due to their workload may delay the referral and when they are unable to handle the problem behaviors, removal will be the short-term solution.. This study surveys preschool teachers working in the Permata Negara Centers in Peninsular Malaysia to examine teachers' sense of self- efficacy to problem behavior. Specifically, the study address teachers beliefs on their competency in handling problem behavior, the kind of support they receive from their organization committee, how useful are those support to address problem behaviors and the referral and removal consequences. Teachers will be given a combination of three Likert scale questionnaires' to be rated online. Teachers' Self-Efficacy, Early Childhood Job Satisfaction Survey (ECJSS) and Working with Challenging Behavior Preschool Survey (WCBPS), these three instruments was adapted to answer 8 research questions and 8 hypothesis, predicted from the literature review. The data analysis method will be descriptive analysis and multiple regression analysis. The findings of the study is expected to be generalized to other early childhood care and education centers in the government and private sectors in Malaysia.*

Keyword: Teacher's sense of self-efficacy, Problem Behavior, Organization Climate

INTRODUCTION

Teachers are always been responsible to ensure the delivery of quality programs in their practice. The new roles of the contemporary early childhood teachers are such as planning for what children will learn, guiding and teaching so that children learn, assessing what children learn, and arranging the classroom environment so that children learn (George S. Morrison, 2014). Among all the key points of providing a successful early year's programs, behavior management is very crucial. Teacher's knowledge of each child helps them to plan appropriately challenging curriculum and to

tailor instructions that responds to each child's strength and needs (Statement, 2005). Inability of teachers to handle the behavior issues in the classroom often leads to distress situation. Challenging behaviors in the classroom often interferes the classroom learning and teaching sessions. It is very crucial for early year's teachers to know, and identify between the typical behavior and challenging behavior. Screening or early identification to detect developing behavior problems is as important as knowing the functions of the behavior. This research focuses on identifying teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the role of organization climate to referral and removal consequences. The study will be conducted in Pusat Permata Negara (PMN) in Peninsular

Malaysia with the sample size derived from teachers teaching children age 4 years old and below.

Problem Statement

When children enter school, teachers become the important person to seek and provide information about children's behavior in the school context. The concern of most preschool teachers is the problem behaviors exhibit by children in the classroom. Preschool teachers often find it challenging on how to address problem behaviors among children in the classroom. Problem behaviors such as non-compliance, academic disengagement and aggression which interferes with the classroom instructional planning and learning sessions (Barton- arwood, Wehby, Gunter & Lane 2016). Some problem behaviors among young children is also an indication of developing at risk features of special needs like infantile autism, attention deficit disorder, attention deficit hyperactive disorder, though there's no clear diagnosis from the medical practitioners. Including children with problem behaviors in the classroom is always a mixed feeling for the mainstream classroom teachers. Teachers sense of efficacy beliefs are important in classroom management (Toran, 2017) . Most mainstream teachers are lack of knowledge and skills in behavior management especially the more severe ones. A survey study conducted on 300 Malaysian primary school teachers indicates that Malaysian teachers do not have sufficient training and skills to support children with additional learning needs (Bailey, Nomanbhoy, & Tubpun, 2015). Teachers feel they are unable to include children with problem behaviors in the mainstream classroom because they are lacking in terms of exposure and training for diverse learners compared to special education teachers (Nornadia Mohamad Razali, Hasnah Toran, Sazlina Kamaralzaman, Norshidah Mohamad Salleh & Mohd. Hanafi Mohd. Yasin 2013). This is why more commonly problem behaviors exhibit by children are misunderstood by teachers as disciplinary issues hence disciplinary actions are taken instead of intervention or referral.

This study is about to examine teachers sense of self- efficacy to problem behavior and the kinds of behavior supports they received from the work place climate. Teachers sense of self-efficacy is found crucial for behavior management in the preschool education. When teachers are confident enough, they are able to construct a treatment plan and removal rate in the preschools can be reduced. Once teachers perceive the knowledge of what is keeping the behavior going, teachers can start implementing strategies to reduce the behavior by altering the way teachers and others responding to it, hence teaching the child more appropriate ways of getting the needs met. When teachers are unable to handle and intervene children with behavior issues, more often children are being rejected in the mainstream schools though there are found to have high cognitive skills. This makes the inclusive education impossible to be implemented in the public service schools. For a successful inclusion, the effort and experience must

be provided to the children at the early years itself with positive behavior supports. To form a high performing education system, inclusive education is being recognized by government in the Malaysia Educational Blueprint.

Literature Review

Problem behavior refers to any type of behavior that interferes with a child's cognitive, social, or emotional development. It is found inappropriate because it is harmful to a child, his peers or adults around them (Kaiser & Rasminsky, 2009). Problem behaviors or also referred as challenging behaviors is one of the core feature of children at risk of developing special needs. Problem behavior which is inappropriate to situation, repetitive and not age appropriate are some early alarm for parents and teachers of young children. In 2014, The US Census Bureau estimated a population of approximately 1.8 billions of youth from 5 to 19 years around the world (States & Report, 2015). Similarly there was a community study conducted to estimate the prevalence of children and adolescence with mental and emotional disorders from 27 countries and every world region. The meta- analysis study indicated a pooled estimation of 13.4% (241 million) children and adolescents affected by any type of mental disorders. The most common group of mental disorders are anxiety disorders, affecting 117 million; disruptive behavior disorder, affecting 113 million; ADHD, affecting 63 million; and depressive disorders, affecting 47 million (Polanczyk, Salum, Sugaya, Caye, & Rohde, 2015).

Problem behaviors related to emotional disturbance pose by young children in the early childhood programs classroom, is to be found very disruptive during the teaching and learning sessions. Some problem behaviors are so defiant, that the early childhood teachers are failing to predict the cause of it. Problem behaviors are also associated with social and emotional disturbance. Some of the social and emotional disturbance defined under the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) of 1977, relevant to problem behavior which persist over a long time of period, that affects a students' educational performance are as following (Lerner, Lowenthal, & Egan, 2003).

- a. An inability to build or maintain satisfactory interpersonal relationships with peers and teacher;
- b. Inappropriate types of behavior or feelings under normal circumstances;
- c. A general pervasive mood of unhappiness or depression; and
- d. A tendency to develop physical symptoms or fears associated with personal or school problems.

A study carried out in Turkey, on early childhood behavior problems and teacher's view, teacher's perception on 36 to 72 month old children with behavior problem (Yumus & Bayhan, 2016). In view of this research, early childhood educators in the Turkish Education System have insufficient knowledge and skills for understanding of behavior problems, developing daily task suitable for the children's interest and needs. Educator's age, level of education and teaching experience and teachers' sense of self-efficacy are the contributing factors for teachers' inability handling children who are at risk of behavior problems. The findings also indicated that, teachers are unable to employ

the proper strategy to deal with behavior problems. Inexperience in understanding children's behavior problems, unable teachers to structure an appropriate intervention plans for treatment. Improper intervention will not only fail to solve the behavior problem but also increase the tendency for more behavior issues to emerge. There is lack of research on preschool educators' role and competencies or self-efficacy coping with these difficulties and mainly the emotional ones, which are often under-recognized (Poulou, 2015).

Teachers' Sense of Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is a construct from the social cognitive theory posited by Albert Bandura. Self-efficacy refers to an individual's beliefs (confident) about his or her capabilities to execute a specific task within a given context (Stajkovic, 2002). The strength of people's convictions in their own effectiveness is likely to affect whether they will even try to cope with given situations (Bandura, 1977). In applying acquired skills having strong self-efficaciousness intensifies and sustains the effort needed for optimal performance, which is difficult to achieve if one is plagued by self-doubts (Bandura, 1982). There upon, to perceive a high self-efficacy towards problem behavior teachers' must have consistent trainings, sufficient practice on the perceived and newly learnt skills and guided supervision to increase their competencies in work situations. People must experience sufficient success using what they have learned to believe in themselves and in the value of the new ways (Bandura, 1988).

In this study the Permata Negara early childhood program teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior is the research concern. Teachers' sense of self-efficacy towards children's problem behavior in the early childhood programs in Malaysia is a primary concern to addressed in this research. Teachers' sense of self-efficacy is measured in the past studies across various educational construct from preschools to tertiary education including pre-service teachers in

Malaysia. There are many empirical studies conducted on teacher's sense of self-efficacy focusing pedagogical practices but specifically less in problem behavior among young children in the early childhood programs. Teachers' teaching efficacy is the most shared construct, research studies like to explore. Teaching efficacy upon 122

trainee teachers of University Of Science Malaysia was measured in a study. The research found that, the trainee teachers perceive high level of self-efficacy in classroom management, teaching strategies and student engagement. Whereas, low self-efficacy was reported when facing students with problem behaviors (Ahmad Zamri Khairani 2017).

Specific to problem behavior, there was a study conducted on 60 special education teachers under the division of special education Malaysia. The purpose of the research was to range the level of special education teachers' knowledge towards behavior management in the special education classroom. Findings reported, teachers in special education

programs have high level of knowledge and are able to manage students problem behavior (Noor Aini Ahmad, & NorHafizah Abu Hanifah 2015). Similarly, a very pioneer study conducted on teachers perception on inclusive education in Malaysia, indicates that inclusive classroom could be successfully implemented if the level of teacher's competency is increased. Opportunities to attend courses, pedagogical adjustment and collaboration with the organization are found to be some factors contributing to teachers' high self-efficacy (Manisah Mohd Ali, Ramlee Mustapha, & Zalizan Mohd Jelas, 2006). Besides that, emotional competency including self-awareness, social awareness, self-management and relationship management groups play an important role in improving self-efficacy among preschool teachers (Ali et al., 2006). Malaysian teachers are also found unprepared for inclusive education, and that addressing teacher's attitude towards inclusion, building up teachers confidence (efficacy) and skills and challenging negative of children at-risk and their families should be government priorities for further professional development (Bailey, Nomanbhoy, & Tubpun 2015). While so many studies conducted focusing on inclusive education, less studies conducted specifically on teachers' perception on their self-efficacy to problem behavior in the preschool environment. Most inclusion studies were conducted in the primary and secondary mainstream schools, unfortunately less in early childhood programs. Therefore the need to study problem behavior and teacher's self-efficacy and the role of organization climate at the preschool level is needed for a successful inclusion classroom in accordance to Malaysian's Education Blueprint (2013-2025).

The Role of Organizational Climate

Organization climate (OC) is derived from the field theory and a scholarly work by Benjamin Schneider. Organizational climate refers to the working environment one employs to. The climate of organization may be conceived as the "personality" of the organization; that is, climate is to organization as personality is to individual (Hoy, Tarter, & Kottkamp, 1991). Organizational behaviors is about understanding employees' perceptions of the work environment and how these perceptions influence individuals' work related attitudes and behaviors. Individual's own perception of the work environment constitute psychological climate at the climate has been proposed as an organizational or unit level construct (Schulte, Ostroff, & Kinicki, 2006). In this study organization climate is used to explain the relationship between teacher's sense of self-efficacy towards problem behavior and the additional support they receive from the working environment. When teachers are supporting children with diverse needs in the classroom, organization climate is expected to support the teachers for students achievement. Specific to the context of teaching, the environment in which people operate including family, schools or workplaces and the persons with whom they interacts on daily basis, may offer enabling resources in given domains of functioning (Zee, 2016). Organization climate is found to be a predictor for teachers' sense of self-efficacy in problem behavior. The result from a study conducted, showed that variables like, principals leadership and teachers collegiality was a

significant predictors for professional commitments among teachers (Collie, Shapka, & Perry, 2011). Organization particularly principals instructional leadership quality is also found to be a factor influencing teachers' sense of self-efficacy (Masita Mohammad Yusof, Azizi Muda, Ahmad Makmom Abdullah, Bahaman Abu Samah, Ramli Basri, & Niriati A. Rashid 2013). (Mehdinezhad & Mansouri, 2016) found out in a study about school principals leadership behaviors and its relation with teachers' sense of self-efficacy that, there is a significant positive between the components of teachers' sense of self-efficacy and principals leadership behaviors and principals leadership behaviors significantly predicted teachers' sense of self-efficacy. On the other hand, teachers behavior could determine a positive school climate because the way teachers perceive their work, relationship with principals and other teachers determine the school climate. Both principals behavior and teachers behavior influence organization climate (Nurharani Selamat, Nur Zahira Samsu, & Nur Shamina Mustafa Kamalu, 2013). In Malaysia the discussions on the leadership and management of preschool education are limited. The specific focus on the impacts of leadership in public preschools is rarely discussed (Farah Laili Muda Ismail, 2013)

Research Method

Quantitative research is a type of educational research in which the researcher decides what to study, ask specific, narrow questions, collect quantifiable data from participants; analyze these numbers using statistics; and conducts the inquiry in an unbiased, objective manner (Creswell, 2008). In this study, the survey research design will be used for data collection, sampling frame and data analysis. Survey designs are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the

population (Creswell, 2008). A cross sectional survey research will be conducted in this study to collect data about teacher's sense of self-efficacy in problem behavior in the Permata Negara organization climate currently. Reason behind theselection of this research design is to measure the current practices of early childhood education teachers to problem behavior among young children in Permata Negara centers. This research method is widely selected for research studies because it is easy to conduct, data can be collected quickly, large sample can be used, information can be obtained directly and results can be generalized accurately and effectively to the population of interest (Chua, Y. P., 2016)

Sampling

At the most specific level, researcher has chosen the PERMATA NEGARA early childhood teachers from the target population as the sample for this study. The researcher will employ purposeful sampling procedure for the purpose of this study and the

samples are the Permata Negara Center teachers. The samples for this study is selected purposefully from the population of the target group because it is the most newest early childhood program introduced in the country. From the population the research intent to study teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behaviors and the kinds of support teachers receive from the organization. There are 88 Permata Negara Centers in Malaysia as in total. Only the Peninsular Permata centers teachers will be selected as sample size of this study.. There are 72 Permata Negara centers operating currently in Peninsular Malaysia (Bahagian Permata 2017). Permata Negara offers early childhood education for children of the age 4 years old and below. From the teacher population, the samples of the study will be the teachers who are teaching children age 4 years old and below. This is because most challenging behavior emerged and seen clearly in between the age of 1 to 4 years old. In the year of 2017 there are

13 states in Peninsular Malaysia operating the Permata Negara centers. The states are Johor Bahru, Kedah, Kelantan, Kuala Lumpur, Melaka, Negeri Sembilan, Pahang, Perak, Perlis, Pulau Pinang, Putrajaya, Selangor and Terengganu. There are 427 teachers in total in the 88 Permata Negara Centers in Malaysia. From the population only teachers from the Peninsular Malaysia is selected for the study. The sample size will 356 teachers as whole. According to Krejcie & Morgan, the suggested sample size for this population is approximately around 306 teachers (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970). Researcher on purpose is maintaining sample size more than 306 in case if any of the participants is unable to follow the study by default.

Data Analysis

Researcher will employ SPSS and AMOS version 22 as a statistical procedures to answer research questions and the hypothesis. Both descriptive challenges and coping strategies. The research explored statistics and inferential statistics will be used to draw conclusion from the sample selected. Research Questions 1, 2 and 3 will be examined using the descriptive statistics and remaining 5 research questions will be examined using multiple regression analysis. Table 1 below shows a brief idea of the methodology of this research

No	Research Questions	Research Objectives	Hypothesis	Instrument	Items	Resource	Method of Data Analysis
	What is teachers' sense of Self Efficacy to students engagement, instructional strategies and classroom management to students problem behavior in Permata Negara based on gender, level of education and years of experience?	To justify, Teachers' sense of self- efficacy to students problem behavior in Permata Negara based and years of experience.		Teachers' sense of self- efficacy scale. Subscale: a) Student Engagement. b) Instructional Strategies. c) Classroom Management	24 items	(Tschannen - Moran and Hoy 2001).	Descriptive Analysis.
	To what extent do teachers in Permata Negara center have access to behavior support and their perception on service utility.	To range the extent of behaviour support the Permata Negara teachers have in their working climate		Part A: Demographic Items. a) Gender b) Experience c) Education	4 items	Bloom 2010	Descriptive Analysis
				Part B: Challenging	5 items		

		Children in the classroom.		
		a) Number of children with challenging behaviour in last 6 month.		
		b) steps that took place.		
		c)total removal		
		d) total number of referral		
What kind of response do Permata Negara teachers report using to address problem behaviour?	To identify the kind of responses teachers are having at Permata Negara report, using to address challenging behavior.	Part C: Early Childhood Job Satisfaction Survey (ECJSS) Subscales i) Co-Worker Relation ii) Supervisor Relation iii) The nature of the Work iv) Working Condition v) Pay & Promotion Opportunitie	50 items	Bloom 2010

What is the relationships between the components of teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the relationship with workplace climate to access to supports, utility of supports and consequences of supports?	To examine the relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the workplace climate at Permata Negara, access to the availability of supports, utility of supports and beliefs about consequences of support for behavioral issues?	<i>H¹: There is positively significant relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the workplace climate access to the availability of supports.</i> <i>H²: There is positively significant relationship between teachers sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the workplace climate to utility of supports.</i>	Working with Challenging Behavior Preschool Survey (WCBPS) Subscales: i) The availability of Support ii) The perceived utility of support iii) The beliefs about consequences of support.	26 Items	By Shauna Miller (2014)	Multiple Regression Analysis
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		Multiple Regression Analysis				
		<i>H3: There is positively significant relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the workplace climate to beliefs about consequences of support.</i>				
What is the relationship between the components of teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's removal rate?	To analyze the relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's removal rates.	<i>H4: There is positively significant relationship between teachers sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's removal rates.</i>	Working with Challenging Behavior Preschool Survey (WCBPS)	26 Items	By Shauna Miller 2014	Multiple Regression Analysis

What is the relationship between the components of teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's referral rate?	To analyze the relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's referral rates.	<i>H5 : There is positively significant relationship between teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the organization's referral rate.</i>	Working with Challenging Behavior Preschool Survey (WCBPS)	26 Items	By Shauna Miller (2014)	Multiple Regression Analysis
What is the relationship between student's problem behavior and referral and removal rates at Permata Negara Centers ?	To analyze the relationship between student's problem behavior and referral and removal rates at Permata Negara Centers?	<i>H6 : There is positively significant relationship between student's problem behavior and referral rates in Permata Negara centers.</i>	Working with Challenging Behavior Preschool Survey (WCBPS)	26 Items	By Shauna Miller (2014)	Multiple Regression Analysis
Does student's problem behavior	To determine student's problem behavior is a	<i>H8 : Student's problem behavior is a mediating</i>	Working with Challenging Behavior	26 Items	By Shauna Miller (2014)	Multiple Regression Analysis

mediate the	mediating	<i>relationship</i>	Preschool
relationship	relationship	<i>between</i>	Survey
between	between	<i>teachers'</i>	(WCBPS)
teacher's	teacher's	<i>sense of self-</i>	
sense of self-	sense of self-	<i>efficacy and</i>	
efficacy and	efficacy and	<i>referral and</i>	
removal and	referral and	<i>removal rates</i>	
referral rates?	removal rates	<i>n Permata</i>	
	in Permata	<i>Negara</i>	
	Negara	<i>centers.</i>	
	centers?		

CONCLUSION

The research procedures planned for this study is explained. This is a quantitative research and development study. This research is involving a number of 351 sample size of preschool teachers teaching in the Permata Program Centers in Peninsular Malaysia. Researcher is using 3 web based instruments to collect data. This is a cross-sectional survey design to examine teachers' sense of self-efficacy to problem behavior and the role of organization climate in referrals and removals.

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